

From: DeCock, Kevin (CDC/CGH/DGHA)
Sent: Wed, 23 Apr 2014 06:09:59 +0000
To: 'Perry, Katherine M'; Parnell, Isiah L; Freeman, Karen (KENYA/OD); Tom Logan (TLogan@wrp-nbo.org); Godec, Robert F; Greenwald, Michael N; Snipes, Christopher K
Subject: RE: Confidential/ Report of Infant Death

Katherine

Noted, thank you. Pse share info when available. not clear from Melanie Bacon's report what actually happened.

KDC

From: Perry, Katherine M (b) (6)
Sent: Tuesday, April 22, 2014 6:36 PM
To: Parnell, Isiah L; DeCock, Kevin (CDC/CGH/DGHA); Freeman, Karen (KENYA/OD); Tom Logan (TLogan@wrp-nbo.org); Godec, Robert F; Greenwald, Michael N; Snipes, Christopher K
Subject: RE: Confidential/ Report of Infant Death

Isiah,

I will share the autopsy report once it is released (in two weeks or so). Not sure of the facility this was carried out in however this was a NIH/PEPFAR sponsored Implementation Science study case.

Best,

Katherine

Katherine M. Perry
PEPFAR Coordinator, Kenya

From: Parnell, Isiah L
Sent: Tuesday, April 22, 2014 6:25 PM
To: Perry, Katherine M; DeCock, Kevin; Freeman, Karen (KENYA/OD); Tom Logan (TLogan@wrp-nbo.org); Godec, Robert F; Greenwald, Michael N; Snipes, Christopher K
Subject: RE: Confidential/ Report of Infant Death

Horrible news. Looping in Amb G and PAS. Pls share autopsy results once known. I take it that this procedure was performed by a person and in a facility well and favorably known to us? Isiah

SBU

This email is UNCLASSIFIED.

From: Perry, Katherine M
Sent: Tuesday, April 22, 2014 6:14 PM

To: DeCock, Kevin; Freeman, Karen (KENYA/OD); Tom Logan (TLogan@wrp-nbo.org)
Cc: Parnell, Isiah L
Subject: Confidential/ Report of Infant Death

Dear All,

Sadly, we have a report of an infant death 20 hours post circumcision here in Kenya. Please read e-mail below.

I am doing as OGAC requested me to do and this is to notify the most senior leadership from CDC, USAID and DOD only. OGAC has asked that if there are any queries received that they should be directed to me and I will forward to OGAC for their response.

Thank you and please let me know if there are any questions. I am sure this will leak quite quickly but we will do what we can to contain this for now. We all realize that the baby's death may not have been related to the circumcision. Awaiting autopsy results.

Best,

Katherine

Katherine M. Perry
PEPFAR Coordinator, Kenya

From: Reed, Jason B
Sent: Tuesday, April 22, 2014 5:28 PM
To: Perry, Katherine M
Cc: Sessle, Erica J; Campbell, Allison K; Meoli, Florence (Lory) B; Ryan, Caroline A; Martin, Julia C; Laube MacDonald, Catharine H
Subject: Re: Report of Infant Death

Hi Katherine,

I have sad news to relay per the email below from Melanie Bacon at NIH. Relevant parties at OGAC are also copied, and Ambassador Bix is aware.

Typically, the rare reports of death originate from in-country and make their way to HQ, per the reporting requirements. In this instance, the death occurred as part of a research study, and NIH HQ was notified immediately. We're confident that the IRB and NIH-dictated investigations will yield conclusive results soon.

The senior-most CDC, USAID, and DOD leaders in Kenya should be alerted in confidence of the death, in case they receive inquiries. Should inquiries be received by the agencies, they should be directed to you, and we can then provide assistance as needed to help coordinate a response (if warranted). Catey Laube from the HQ MC TWG's Communications Sub-group is also copied, in case PA requires support.

If you would prefer for me to notify the agency leads in Kenya, please let me know. I will also alert the HQ MC TWG Co-chairs, per the reporting requirements.

Thank you for your consideration and appreciating the confidential and sensitive nature of the information. Please advise on how you wish to proceed, and I will ensure we provide whatever support is needed.

All the best, Jason

Jason Reed, MD, MPH
Senior Technical Advisor/Epidemiologist
Office of the U.S. Global AIDS Coordinator

From: Bacon, Melanie (NIH/NIAID) [E] [<mailto:mbacon@niaid.nih.gov>]
Sent: Tuesday, April 22, 2014 09:58 AM Eastern Standard Time
To: Reed, Jason B
Subject: Report of Infant Death

Hello Jason,

I am sending this message to let you know that today the Kenya team carrying out the NIH/PEPFAR sponsored Implementation Science study, *Integration of infant male circumcision with community health services in Kenya*, will be reporting to their IRB and the Kenyan National VMMC Task Force on the death of an infant last week who had recently been circumcised. At this time, we feel that the death is unlikely to be due to the circumcision procedure, however the timing of the death, only 20 hours later, requires us to consider all possibilities – even if remote. All the routine procedures for infant circumcision in the Kenyan program were followed, the child appeared healthy during the procedure and tolerated it well. While lidocaine was used for anesthesia, the half life is short and an allergy or toxicity reaction the following day would be very unlikely. The child had had some difficulty breathing a couple hours after the procedure and was brought back to the clinic. He was treated and observed for several hours before he was released, appearing stable. He was found having “convulsions” the next morning and had died by the time he arrived at the hospital. An autopsy has been performed and the report is expected back within 2 weeks, we will share any new information at that time.

You may inform others who are directing PEPFAR sponsored programs in Kenya, in case they hear anything about it they will know the facts and can respond appropriately. However, this should be a confidential FYI, rather than broadly distributing it, in respect for the family’s privacy and to allow the Kenyan IRB to conduct its review without pressure from outside.

Please let me know if you have any questions.

Thank you,
Melanie

Melanie C. Bacon, RN, MPH
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From: Chege, Wairimu (NIH/NIAID) [E]
Sent: Mon, 23 Jun 2014 11:33:21 +0000
To: DeCock, Kevin (CDC/CGH/DGHA)
Subject: RE: HPTN annual meeting?

Dear Kevin,

It was a distinct pleasure to see you at the HPTN annual meeting this past week! I hope that you have had safe travels back to Kenya.

I was mentioning to you that there is a planned study in Homa Bay looking at combined HIV prevention interventions for youth. The KEMRI/CDC lab in Kisumu will be providing support. There will also be a small sub-component of PrEP for young girls, and I believe that this can and will contribute to NASCOP's plans for PrEP in the country.

I will send you a more formal message regarding the study and the site visit. It is slated for mid to late August.

Another planned study is an HPTN study looking at feasibility of delivering voluntary medical male circumcision to MSM in various settings. Several sites, including Kenya, have applied to participate. This study is in early stages of protocol development, sites have not yet been selected, funding has not yet been secured, etc. I'm sure you will hear more of this going forward.

Thanks so much once again for your consistent graciousness and guidance and shining example. Even the few minutes in the hallways at these conferences is of utmost importance and I thank you greatly for that.

I hope to see you in Kenya in August!

Thanks,
Wairimu

From: DeCock, Kevin (CDC/CGH/DGHA)
Sent: Monday, June 16, 2014 3:35 AM
To: Chege, Wairimu (NIH/NIAID) [E]
Subject: Re: HPTN annual meeting?

Wairimu

I will be there - leaving Brussels this am, arrive DC this afternoon so will be at the meeting. Look forward to seeing you.

Best Kevin

----- Original Message -----

From: Chege, Wairimu (NIH/NIAID) [E]
Sent: Sunday, June 15, 2014 08:41 PM Eastern Standard Time
To: DeCock, Kevin (CDC/CGH/DGHA)
Subject: HPTN annual meeting?

Hi Kevin!

I hope you are doing well. It was swell to bump into you at the CROI 2014 conference in Boston a few months ago. I noticed that you have registered for the HPTN annual meeting here in DC. Will you be attending? If so, it would be lovely to catch up, if your schedule allows. I'll look at my schedule also and perhaps we can identify a

time to just sit and chat, even if briefly. I know it is always hard during these meetings...

Safe travels and I hope to see you!

Thanks,

Wairimu